

A Review of Recent Trends in Production and Operation Management

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Abstract: This paper discusses in the area of recent trends in production management by focusing on the importance and role of green manufacturing, CADM, Employee involvement, and Supply chain management. The analysis is done on how all these trends play an important role in making processes more efficient, reducing operation costs, increasing production rate, product quality, cost-cutting, and making the process faster by maximum usage of man, material, and machine. This development has led to an increase in the wages of workers, creating global marketing increased product design, quality of product, and opportunities for introducing new inventions in product design and customization. The last one is the introduction of green production.

Introduction :

Production/operations management is the process, which combines and transforms various resources used in the production/operations subsystem of the organization into value-added products and services in a controlled manner as per the policies of the organization. Therefore, it is that part of an organization, which is concerned with the transformation of a range of inputs into the required (products and services) having the requisite quality level. The set of interrelated management activities, which are involved in manufacturing certain products, is called production management. If the same concept is extended to services management, then the corresponding set of management activities is called operations management.

Definition :

Production management becomes the acceptable term from the 1930s to the 1950s. As F.W. Taylor's works become more widely known, managers developed techniques that focussed on economic efficiency in manufacturing. Workers were studied in great detail to eliminate wasteful efforts and achieve greater efficiency. At the same time, psychologists, socialists, and other social scientists began to study people and human behavior in the working environment. In addition, economists, mathematicians, and computer socialists contributed newer, more sophisticated analytical approaches. With the 1970s emerges two distinct changes in our views. The most obvious of these, reflected in the new name operations management was a shift in the service and manufacturing sectors of the economy. As the service sector became more prominent, the change from 'production' to 'operations' emphasized the broadening of our field to service

organizations. The second, more suitable change was the beginning of an emphasis on synthesis, rather than just analysis, in management practices.

Objectives of Production and Operation Management :

The objective of production management is 'to produce goods services of right quality and quantity at the right time and right manufacturing cost'.

1. Right Quality

The quality of the product is established based on the customer's needs. The right quality is not necessarily the best quality. It is determined by the cost of the product and the technical characteristics as suited to the specific requirements.

2. Right Quantity

The manufacturing organization should produce the products in the right number. If they are produced in excess of demand the capital will block up in the form of inventory and if the quantity is produced in short of demand, lead to a shortage of products.

3. Right Time

Timeliness of delivery is one of the important parameters to judge the effectiveness of the production department. So, the production department has to make the optimal utilization of input resources to achieve its objective.

4. Right Manufacturing Cost

Manufacturing costs are established before the product is actually manufactured. Hence, all attempts should be made to produce the products at pre-established cost, so as to reduce the variation between actual and the standard (pre-established) cost.

Scope Of Production And Operations Management:

Production and operations management is concerned with the conversion of inputs into

outputs, using physical resources, so as to provide the desired utilities to the customer while meeting the other organizational objectives of effectiveness, efficiency, and adaptability. It distinguishes itself from other functions such as personnel, marketing, finance, etc., by its primary concern for 'conversion by using physical resources.' Following are the activities that are listed under production and operations management functions:

1. Location of facilities
2. Plant layouts and material handling
3. Product design
4. Process design
5. Production and planning control
6. Quality control
7. Materials management
8. Maintenance management.

Recent Trends in production and operation management:

Total Quality Management (TQM)-

Total quality management is the ongoing process of detecting and reducing or eliminating manufacturing errors, streamlining supply chain management, improving the customer experience, and ensuring that employees are properly trained. Total quality management seeks to hold all parties involved in the manufacturing process responsible for the overall quality of the final product or service.

Cycle Time Reduction-

Cycle time is reduced by decreasing time spent on non-value-added activities and simplifying and streamlining the process, lowering the cost of operations.

Benefits of reducing cycle time include faster time-to-market and, if other cost factors are kept in check, the possibility of higher profitability. Reduced cycle time also allows a company to be more competitive with other businesses that offer similar products to the same customer base.

Employee engagement-

Is a vital notion in the endeavor to comprehend and explain the nature of an organization's connection with its employees, both qualitatively and quantitatively. The direct participation of employees in assisting an organization in fulfilling its mission and meeting its objectives by applying their own ideas, knowledge, and efforts to problem-solving and decision-making.

Recent tendencies have been to delegate decision-making and problem-solving

responsibilities to lower levels of the organization. Employee involvement and empowerment are terms used to describe this. Quality circles, for example, and the usage of work teams or quality improvement teams.

Just In Time –

JIT inventory is a management strategy that directly aligns raw-material orders from suppliers with production schedules. Companies use this inventory strategy to increase efficiency and reduce waste by receiving goods only as needed for the manufacturing process, which lowers inventory costs. This method necessitates that producers accurately forecast demand. Kanban is a scheduling system that is frequently used in conjunction with JIT to avoid work-in-process overcapacity.

Computer-Aided Manufacturing-

The use of software and computer-controlled machinery to automate a manufacturing process is known as computer-aided manufacturing (CAM)... By generating toolpaths, the software tells a machine how to make a product. Machinery capable of converting raw materials into finished goods.

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